

EXAMINING ASSOCIATIONS BETWEEN PERCEIVED PARENTAL SUPPORT AND STUDENT'S LEARNING WELLBEING DURING ONLINE LEARNING UNDER COVID-19 CONDITIONS

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Abstract

The global pandemic of COVID-19 had a huge impact on all spheres of life but especially on school and family life. Such a situation posed great challenges especially to teachers, parents or guardians, and students. Being faced with this novel situation, students struggled with planning their day, handling other responsibilities at home, resulting in significant psychological and social effects on the population. Considering these forced changes, students were faced with their demanding roles both as a student and a family member. This study aimed at exploring the associations between perceived parental support and student' learning wellbeing during the pandemic, as well as examine gender differences on perceived parental support. The sample consisted of N=458 university students (19.2% males, 80.8% females) with a mean age of 3.71 years studying at both private and public universities in Albania and recruited via google forms during the peak of the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020. By using a quantitative research design, the results showed that perceived parental support was positively correlated with student' learning wellbeing. The Independent Samples *T*-test analysis also showed that there are no significant gender differences on student's perceived parental support. This study concluded that perceived parental support is an important determinant of student' learning wellbeing during unprecedented times. Therefore, parents should provide unlimited support towards their children and especially towards youth studying at university. They should be able to support them both emotionally and technically by providing more access to digital resources and tools to facilitate their online learning in a home environment.

Keywords: Student, parental support, learning wellbeing, COVID-19.

1. INTRODUCTION

The outbreak of COVID-19 virus has forced all educational institutions to close down and shift into alternative methods of teaching and learning. Such a period had a detrimental impact on students' lives especially on students who were more limited from social contacts and support of their family members. They found themselves under more challenging circumstances struggling with adapting the learning habits, as well as their coping strategies during their learning process. During the lockdown, students had to learn within the

same environment with other family members who were the main ones to provide social support towards them. The COVID-19 pandemic changed fundamentally the way students used to receive knowledge, shifting from the physical classroom to the virtual learning platforms. According to recent research, the amount of time and the quality of online communication with lecturers make a big difference and better facilitate the learning process and satisfaction than conventional face-to-face communication (Ananga & Biney, 2017; Soffer & Nachmias, 2018).

Though, students' engagement with online programmes provides more access to online classes, convenience, and practicality, sometimes it is also challenging (Harris & Martin, 2012). A study conducted by Heyman (2010), showed that students report three aspects that contribute in increasing interest in online classes: student support and the sense of belongingness to the institution; quality of communication between faculty and students; and student self-control. However, students who are faced with unexpected online learning experience more stress which undermines students' well-being during their learning (Grubic et al., 2020, Lyons et al., 2020). Especially, in developing countries like Albania, students are faced with many challenges during the implementation of online learning due to limited internet access or poor internet connectivity and limited digital tools such as a desktop, laptop or ipad. Sometimes, they have to share those digital tools with other siblings who are also engaged with online learning.

Though ongoing research suggests that there is a strong relationship between the unprecedented times and people's wellbeing (Saltzman et al. 2020) little research has been done to examine the role of other factors such as parental support on college students' well-being during their online learning.

This study was conducted in Albania during the COVID-19 pandemic. The primary purpose of this study was to find out whether there are associations between perceived parental support and students' learning wellbeing. Next, this study also aimed at exploring whether there are gender differences on perceived parental support during online learning. To attain these aims, a quantitative research design was used. This study serves to propel further research into the impact of parental support on students' learning wellbeing, as this is a determining factor in their academic success as well. Parental support is often seen as a dispensable factor, as not extremely necessary for a child's success, often regarded only by one of the parental figures if at all. However, parental support greatly influences students' academic conduct and outcomes. The hypotheses are as follows: 1) There is a positive association between perceived parental support and students' learning wellbeing and 2) There are significant gender differences on perceived parental support such that females are exposed toward higher levels of parental support than males.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Self – Determination Theory (SDT) was used as a theoretical lens to understand the way students stay motivated during online learning and how parental support acting as a social environmental factor enhances their learning during unprecedented times. SDT is a universally acknowledged theory of motivation. Especially during the COVID-19 pandemic, the theory has become a crucial reference in explaining the way people get motivated during online learning and how their surrounding social environment effects their intrinsic motivation. SDT claims that the basic psychological needs for competence, autonomy, and relatedness represent core conditions for personal growth, integration, social development, and psychological well-being. SDT assumes that human beings have evolved biologically to be inherently active, intrinsically motivated, and oriented toward developing naturally through integrative processes that need not be learned; they are inherent in human nature. As such, being curious, vital and self-motivated are considered as positive and persistent features of human nature (Deci & Ryan, 2000). These qualities develop over time, play a crucial role in learning, and are affected by social environments.

As stated by Deci and Ryan (2000), these needs are understood as underlying the adaptive organization of behavior and being supported by many individual adaptations, rather than themselves being functionally specific. Additionally, this theory links environmental factors to fundamental human needs as a basis for explaining effects of the social environment on intrinsic motivation. The authors have been focusing more on the psychological nutrients and their influences within the social environments (Ryan & Deci, 2000). According to SDT, intrinsic motivation is considered as a main feature of human beings and is viewed as the prototype of psychological freedom or self-determination. This characteristic can be either undermined or developed depending on whether the social environment supported or discouraged the needs for competence and self-determination. Positive feedback and choice help improve experiences of competence and self-determination leading to increased levels of intrinsic motivation (Deci et al., 1999). Human beings are more likely to function effectively when the needs for competence, autonomy and relatedness are

satisfied. Such conditions then, promote more optimal learning, skilled performance and prosocial behavior.

SDT has proposed strong relationship between parental support and students' learning (Grolnick & Ryan, 1989). This theory suggests that parental support and control are two important parenting practices that influence students' learning and academic achievement. Parents who use a more autonomy-supportive style of parenting are more likely to foster independence on children's decision-making, approach more rationally to their decisions and better understand children's emotions (Bureau & Mageau, 2014). Studies show that parental support may undermine several health-related behaviors among young people such as Internet dependency by monitoring the time spent online and encouraging students stay on task and use the internet more effectively for their academic purposes (Varma, Cheaskul, & Poonpol, 2018).

3. METHODS

3.1 Sample

This study was part of a huge study on learning during COVID-19 (Pelikan et al., 2021) where Albania was among the countries included in this study initiated by the University of Vienna. The sample included in this study is representative of the Albanian university students comprised of 458 students (19.2% males, 80.8% females) with a mean age of 3.71 years. The subjects were undergraduate and graduate students studying at both private and public universities in Albania.

3.2 Measurement tool

An online survey designed on Google forms was distributed to the participants. The questionnaire aimed at obtaining information relying on self-reported data about the respondents' challenges and experiences with digital teaching and learning in higher education institutions and perceived parental support during the COVID-19 pandemic in Albania. The first part consisted of questions about the participants' socio-demographic information. The second part consisted mostly of single choice questions, including a rating scale from (1) strongly agree to (5) strongly disagree. It also included some questions with "Yes or No" answers. The questionnaire took about fifteen minutes to be filled out.

3.3 Data collection procedure

The data were collected with online questionnaires via Google forms during 2020. The participants were recruited by distributing the link of the online questionnaire. Participants were informed about the study's goals, inclusion criteria for participation, i.e., attending public and private universities in Albania, and the complete anonymity of their data. All students participated voluntarily and only those who provided a response of consent were included in the sample. The data were collected during the lockdown period of both private and public universities.

3.4 Measures

Perceived parental support. This variable was measured with 5 items, and it was created by combining both maternal and paternal support. The participants reported on how difficult it was for them to obtain certain basic requirements from their parents such as (1) care and warmth; (2) discussing over personal topics; (3) getting advice on their studies; (4) getting advice on other personal projects; (5) getting help on other personal cases. A 4-point response scale was used to answer these questions (1 = *very difficult*, 2 = *difficult*, 3 = *easy*, 4 = *very easy*).

Learning wellbeing. This part, involving students' wellbeing, required the respondents to answer regarding their *engagement and flow* in their studies, variable which was measured completely absorbed in the university works; and (3) being so involved in the university works that no longer being able to notice what is happening around; and also regarding *perseverance*, variable that was measured by (1) *finishing whatever task that the student's begins to work on*; (2) *keeping at the task until done*; and (3) *sticking to the plan to study, once they plan to*. The same 5-point scale was used in this section as well.

Demographics. Among the main demographic data used in this study was gender. Gender was measured by a single choice answer on the items (1) *male*; (2) *female*; (3) and *other*.

The total score of these aforementioned variables from the questionnaire was computed for the statistical analyses.

4. RESULTS

4.1 Statistical Analysis

This work employed a quantitative analysis of using IBM-SPSS statistics version 22. Initially, the data were screened for missing values, outliers, creating scales, checking reliability of scales such as Cronbach's alpha values, checking violations of the assumptions for multivariate analyses, conducting necessary transformations of the variables of interest, and creating an intercorrelation matrix for all study variables.

Next, statistical analyses were conducted including a variety of techniques that were related to univariate and bivariate analyses. Initially, an Independent Samples *T*-test was conducted to examine whether there were gender differences on student's perceived parental support. In addition, a bivariate Pearson correlation analysis was conducted to investigate whether there is a positive correlation between student learning wellbeing and perceived parental support.

4.2 Descriptive Statistics

As shown in Table 1, the means, min, max values, standard deviations, skewness and kurtosis are provided for all study variables.

Table 1

Mean, standard deviation, standardized skewness, standardized kurtosis, minimum and maximum values for the key variables (N=458)

	Min.	Max.	M	SD	S. Skewness	S. Kurtosis
Student wellbeing	1	5	3.59	0.96	-0.37	-0.61
Perceived parental support	1	5	3.34	1.15	-0.36	-1.16

Note: M = Mean; SD = Standard Deviation

4.3 Independent Samples *T*-test Analyses

In order to answer the research question on whether there are gender differences on students perceived parental support, an Independent Samples *T*-test analysis was conducted. As indicated in Table 2, the Independent Samples *T*-test analysis revealed that females did not significantly differ from males on perceived parental support ($p = .74$).

Table 2

Comparison of male vs. female student's perceived parental support on learning during COVID-19 pandemic (N=458)

Variable	M(SD)	t	p
Perceived parental support		0.34	0.74
Male	1.6 (.49)		
Female	1.62 (.49)		

4.4 Bivariate Pearson Correlation Analysis

As indicated in Table 3, bivariate analysis was conducted where Pearson correlation analysis showed a positive correlation between student learning wellbeing and perceived parental support, $r(458) = .15$, $p = .002$ which would be considered a medium effect size (Cohen, 1988).

Table 3

Intercorrelations for the main variables of the study (N=458)

Variable	1
Student wellbeing	...
1. Perceived parental support	0.15

* $p < .001$

5. DISCUSSION

This study aimed to investigate the links between perceived parental support and students' learning wellbeing during the COVID-19 pandemic in online settings. This work also aimed at examining whether there are gender differences on perceived parental support during students' online learning. Regarding the first research question on whether there are gender differences on students perceived parental support, the results revealed that females did not significantly differ from males on perceived parental support. Findings are inconsistent with regard to gender differences on parental support. In contrast to this finding, the work of Gilligan (1982) suggests that girls hold a more "social" perspective in moral decision-making and that separation and individuation are critically tied to identity formation for boys, but not girls. This happens due to the fact that separation from the mother is essential to the development of masculinity but not femininity. Gilligan's work suggests that girls might invest more time and effort in social relationships than boys, and value relational intimacy in a different way compared to boys (Rueger, Malecki, & Demaray, 2008). In line with these findings, another study shows that there exist gender differences in the structure of perceived social support and that these differences can be explained by socialization experiences and social roles associated with gender (Matud, Ibañez, Bethencourt, Marrero, & Carballeira, 2003). These results are supported by another study conducted in Spain and Portugal with undergraduate emerging adults aged between 18 and 29 years suggested that gender-differentiated socialization patterns persist during emerging adulthood and that these patterns may be affected by the sociocultural context (García-Mendoza, Parra, Sánchez-Queija, Oliveira, & Coimbra, 2022). All these studies have been conducted with young people focusing more on adolescents.

The second research question was related to the links between perceived parental support and student's learning wellbeing. The results revealed that parental support plays an important role on students' commitment to learning and their academic success. This finding is in line with other studies showing that those students whose parents had higher support and expectations for their children's academic work performed better and progresses faster academically than those who are not provided with sufficient parental support (Wolf, Sax & Harper, 2009; Seider, 2012). Consistently, another study conducted with adolescent boys and girls in Iceland found that parental factors such as parental support and monitoring are all associated with academic achievement (Kristjánsson, & Sigfúsdóttir, 2009).

This study comes along with several limitations. Firstly, the sample included a relatively high number of participants but female students are overrepresented as a population in higher education in Albania therefore, the number of male students was lower which might have an impact on controlling for gender differences on perceived parental support. Secondly, this study used a single method to collect data because of the lockdown due to the COVID-19 pandemic, but using a mixed-method approach could have provided a broader understanding of these factors. Lastly, this study considered only two measures namely, perceived parental support and student's learning wellbeing. There might be other measures that could have contributed in better understanding the influence of other factors on student's learning wellbeing in online settings. Further research can consider other factors to have an impact on student's learning especially under unusual circumstances such as with the COVID-19 pandemic.

6. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The lockdown due to the COVID-19 pandemic and challenges with preventing it, forced many higher educational institutions to shift into online teaching and learning for both teachers and students around the globe. This lockdown revealed emerging disadvantages in education systems in developing countries of the world with Albania being no exception. The situation also revealed that flexible and robust education systems are crucial in the face of unprecedented times. Stemming from this, the current study adopted a quantitative survey approach to examine student-reported demographic information, perceived parental support, and online learning wellbeing during the COVID-19 lockdown. The study participants responded to an online Google survey questionnaire where 458 university students from both private and public universities maintaining their anonymity and assuming their answers were truthful, filled in the survey.

The findings revealed that students struggled a lot in planning their day, handling other responsibilities at the same time at home, and they also had very limited access to internet connection or limited access to digital tools especially, students who resided in disadvantaged rural areas. The findings of this study also showed that parental support plays an important role on students' learning wellbeing. The results have reflected a developmental sequence, such that earlier family support processes enable the child to establish a better academic status and positive self-concept which then contributes to the child's personality and career development.

Therefore, parents should provide unlimited support towards their children and especially towards youth studying at university. They should be able to support them both emotionally and technically by providing more access to digital resources and tools to facilitate their online learning in a home environment. Moreover, parents should be informed and supported by the government during exceptional situations so children can have available resources and tools to continue their education via online learning.

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